

Ekaterina Bataeva

PRACTICES OF SELF-CONSTITUTION AND DECONSTRUCTION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

The article analyzes the prospects of using the concepts of “self-constitution” (Z. Bauman) and “deconstruction” (J. Derrida) in the context of modern sociology of education. The concepts of “visible” and “invisible pedagogics” (B. Bernstein) in the context of the deconstruction sociology of education is considered. It is shown that in the context of the “self-constitutional” paradigm, the subject of education calls into question any attempts of coding or programming his/her professional or worldview experience, since in this case he/she is deprived of the freedom of self-determination. In the postmodern theory of education, social actors are endowed with the possibility of self-constitution or self-assembly. It is concluded that in the theory of deconstruction, special attention is paid not so much to teaching methods (how teaching), but to content (what learning), which can stimulate intellectual creativity or, conversely, leave a student indifferent. A comparative analysis of the “invisible” and “visible” pedagogics is carried out, in which the programming/coding of the consciousness of students is possible on the basis of subjective ideas of a teacher. It is concluded that “visible pedagogics” may turn out to be more humanistic because of their “visibility”: since a teacher openly manifests his/her principles and requirements, the students have an opportunity to identify and then accept or reject them. As for the “invisible pedagogy”, it is much more difficult to determine how correct it is via that situation that “discursive rules (learning order rules) are known only to the transmitter”.

Key words: self-constitution, deconstruction, constructivism, visible pedagogy, invisible pedagogy.

Батаєва К. В. Практики самоконституювання і деконструкції в системі вищої освіти.

Проаналізовані перспективи використання концептів «самоконституювання» (З. Бауман) і «деконструкції» (Ж. Дерріда) в контексті сучасної соціології освіти. Розглянуто зміст концепцій «видимих» і «невидимих педагогію» (Б. Бернстейн) в контексті деконструктивістської соціології освіти. Показано, що в контексті парадигми «самоконституювання» суб'єкт освіти ставить під сумнів будь-які спроби кодування або програмування його професійного чи світоглядного досвіду, оскільки в цьому випадку він

позбавляється свободи самовизначення. У постмодерністській теорії освіти соціальні актори наділяються можливістю самоконституювання або само-монтажу. Зроблено висновок, що в теорії деконструкції особливу увагу приділено не тільки методам викладання (як-навчання), скільки змісту (що-навчання), який може стимулювати інтелектуальну творчість або, навпаки, залишити студента байдужим. Проведено порівняльний аналіз «невидимої» і «видимої» педагогик, в яких не виключається можливість програмування/кодування свідомості учнів, виходячи з суб'єктивних уявлень педагога про те, які інтелектуальні коди необхідні студентам. Зроблено висновок, що «видимі педагогіки» можуть виявитися більш гуманними в силу їх «видимості»: оскільки викладач відкрито маніфестує свої принципи і вимоги, в учнів залишається можливість ідентифікувати, а потім прийняти їх або відхилити. Що ж стосується «невидимої педагогіки», то саме тому, що її «дискурсивні правила знає тільки транслятор», набагато складніше визначити, наскільки коректними вони є в дійсності.

Ключові слова: самоконституювання, деконструкція, конструктивізм, видимі педагогіки, невидимі педагогіки.

Батаева Е. В. Практики самоконституирования и деконструкции в системе высшего образования.

В статье проанализированы перспективы использования концептов «самоконституирования» (З. Бауман) и «деконструкции» (Ж. Деррида) в контексте современной социологии образования. Рассмотрено содержание концепций «видимых» и «невидимых педагогик» (Б. Бернштейн) в контексте деконструктивистской социологии образования. Показано, что в контексте парадигмы «самоконституирования» субъект образования подвергает сомнению любые попытки кодирования или программирования его профессионального или мировоззренческого опыта, поскольку в этом случае он лишается свободы самоопределения. В постмодернистской теории образования социальные акторы наделяются возможностью самоконституирования или само-монтажа. Сделан вывод, что в теории деконструкции особое внимание уделяется не столько методам преподавания (*как-обучение*), сколько содержанию (*что-обучение*), которое может стимулировать интеллектуальное творчество либо, наоборот, оставить студента равнодушным. Проведен сравнительный анализ «невидимой» и «видимой» педагогик, в которых не исключается возможность программирования/кодирования сознания обучающихся, исходя из субъективных представлений педагога о том, какие интеллектуальные коды необходимы студентам. Сделан вывод,

что «видимые педагогики» могут оказаться более гуманными в силу их «видимости»: поскольку преподаватель открыто манифестирует свои принципы и требования, у обучающихся остается возможность идентифицировать, а затем принять их или отклонить. Что же касается «невидимой педагогики», то именно потому, что ее «дискурсивные правила известны только передающему», гораздо сложнее определить, насколько корректными они являются в действительности.

Ключевые слова: самоконституирование, деконструкция, конструктивизм, видимые педагогики, невидимые педагогики.

In the modern philosophy of education, one can notice an ideological clash of paradigms that interpret the educational situations in different ways – social constructivism, the concept of “self-constitution” by Z. Bauman and “deconstruction” by J. Derrida. If the theory of social constructivism is popular in modern sociology of education, the concepts of “self-constitution” and “deconstruction” have not yet received adequate coverage in modern sociology of education and require in-depth conceptualization [1; 2; 3; 4; 7]. The purpose of the article is to consider the features of application of postmodern concepts of Z. Bauman, J. Derrida in the situation of analysis of problems in higher education.

In the social constructivism, one considers conditions and possibilities of explicit or implicit formation/development of students’ personality through creation of a certain educational environment. In a situation of perception/assimilation of certain values, concepts, ideas translating by educational agents, it is possible to carry out coding/programming of consciousness/worldview of students. The worldview of students can be constructed consciously (if the educational agents, pursuing pedagogical and professional goals, try to reproduce a certain personality model of the student that meets the needs of a society) or unconsciously (if students, while staying in a specific educational interactive situation, involuntarily learn a certain set of norms and values, rules and behaviors created and encouraged by educational agents). In the process of creating worldview constructs, students can take an active part or can act as recipients of intellectual models offered by educational agents. Conscious constructing of the model of creative thinking learner, as a rule, is based on humanistic ideals of a free, intellectually and spiritually mature person, prone to creativeness.

The designing of the student's model can be more or less "subtle" or "rude" (via using "soft" technologies for improving the personality or "hard" methods for transmitting certain "codes" of behavior). Designers can explicitly (through visible and recognizable teaching methods) or implicitly (using latent ways of building competencies through rewards) stimulate the formation of certain behavioral and mental skills of students. However, in certain contexts, educational constructivism may conflict with liberal ideas of freedom of a person, which is endowed with the possibility of disagreement in the construction of codes of thinking or behavior (albeit humanistic codes of thinking or behavior), the possibility of rebellion against any technologies of personality formation. In this point, when human freedom can be somewhat impaired, one can state a conceptual discrepancy between the paradigms of social constructivism and "self-constitution" of the student's personality.

The concept of self-constitution by Z. Bauman reserves the possibility of a free choice of certain educational vectors by a social actor that attract his/her attention not by virtue of its coercion, but because of temptation of their semantic meanings. A student may freely form his/her professional and communicative competencies, making an independent decision, which theoretical and applied disciplines one should study in-depth, which curricula are truly innovative, and which ones can be ignored. The subject in the context of the paradigm of "self-constitution" questions any attempts to encode or recode his/her consciousness, any programming contexts of his/her professional or worldview perception, regardless of their proclaimed context ("humanistic" or "marketable"). Since in a situation of "recoding" or "reprogramming" of consciousness, a subject is already deprived of the freedom of self-determination, since someone else (external actors), and not he/she, decides what his/her linguistic, communicative, professional competences should be, how he/she should be trained (interactively or in the mode of deep self-reflection), what teaching practices he/she should prefer. Therefore, in the postmodern sociology of education, one deconstructs any attempts of imposing to educational subjects the structured models of learning, in which everything is under strict control, in which instructors are endowed with supreme authority to make a decision, how, in what time and in what direction students should develop. Social actors

in the higher education are endowed with the possibility of self-constitution or self-assembly, which is “a finally incomplete process” [8]. According to Z. Bauman, self-constitution does not have a final point, does not have a visible limit, or even a stable direction. “The *self-assembly* of the agency is *not a cumulative process*; self-constitution entails disassembling alongside the assembling, adoption of new elements as much as loss shedding of others, learning together with forgetting” [8, p.194].

Z. Bauman introduces the concept of “orientation points”, which indirectly can “direct the successful movement” of actors of the educational process. The multiplicity of diverse opportunities, the pluralism of development models, the diversity of competing vectors are a randomly scattered set of poles that can be approached or ignored. “Orientation points are substitute for pre-determined patterns for life-projects. ... Thus, freedom of choice and dependence on external agents ... are products of the same process of self-assembly and of the constant demand for reliable orientation points” [8, p.195]. So, in the concept of Z. Bauman, the ideas of constructivism are suspended and uncertain: “orientation points” are allowed to constructing of certain aspects of students’ worldview, although they cannot coerce and control over the practices of reaching these orientations.

Analyzing the prospects of the concept of “self-constitution”, it is possible to distinguish two modes of (re)production of sociocultural learning process described by B. Bernstein: “*what* is transmitted, its content, and *how* they are transmitted; in other words, the “what” and “how” of any transmission” [9]. The “how” mode of knowledge transmission carried out in explicit or implicit, visible or invisible regime of communication, in which hierarchical relations are masked or, conversely, are open positioned has particular importance in the educational process according to B. Bernstein. The theory of “pedagogical practices” by B. Bernstein emphasizes the priority of the so-called “invisible pedagogics”, aimed at “acquiring learners’ competencies” rather than transmitting information (which is the goal of “visible pedagogics”). Invisible pedagogics, which B. Bernstein calls “progressive” (as opposed to conservative “visible pedagogics”), do not exclude the possibility of a hierarchical elevation of a teacher in a situation of educational interaction with students, who secretly/invisibly controls the

learning process, focusing on developing students' competence. "In the case of an *invisible pedagogy* the *discursive rules* (the *rules of the order of instruction*) are *known only* to the *transmitter*, and in this *sense* a *pedagogic practice* of this type is (at least initially) *invisible* to the acquirer, essentially because the acquirer appears to fill the *pedagogic space* rather than the transmitter" [9, p.71]. According to B. Bernstein, the "progressiveness" of invisible pedagogics is manifested not only in the fact that they stimulate the acquisition of competencies by students, but also in the fact that they are "less concentrated on establishing explicit stratifying differences between the acquirers" [9, p.93], contributing to the implementation and development of a wide variety of the abilities of students. "Their focus is not upon a gradable performance of the acquirer, but on the procedures internal to the acquirer (cognitive, linguistic, affective, motivational)" [9, p. 71], allowing students to deviate from the generally accepted canons of thinking and communication.

Despite the obvious "progressive" and humanistic implication of the concept of "invisible pedagogics" by B. Bernstein, there are some doubts about the unambiguity of his attitudes, as well as the expediency of opposing the projects of "visible" and "invisible" pedagogics. Do the attitudes for "acquiring competencies" and for "fulfilling the tasks" exclude each other? Can't the practices of transferring of information and creative development of competences of students be combined in the same communicative and educational situation? It seems that the process of acquiring/developing various competencies not only excludes, but even presupposes a preliminary acquaintance with a certain conceptual context and the assimilation of the transmitted ideas in combination with their subsequent creative and original transformation. In addition, not only "invisible", but also "visible" pedagogics, in which serious attention is paid both to the practice of completing tasks and to the practice of developing students' competencies, may question the "establishment of explicit stratifying differences between the acquirers" and encourage a *different* style of solving the tasks, recognizing *different* ways of the assimilation of information, using *different* criteria for evaluating the learning outcomes of students, refusing the practices of comparing the achievements of students in accordance to "some external standards".

Let us touch upon a more serious problem related to the possibilities of

social modeling of communicative and educational practices of students. If we compare the prospects of the “invisible” and “visible” pedagogics, then, in both contexts the possibility of programming/coding the consciousness of students is not excluded as a teacher subjectively can decide which learning codes have to be cultivated in educational process. At the same time, it is quite obvious that different teachers can emphasize the importance of completely different, and even alternative, programs for the development of students’ competence; they can try to “encode” students’ consciousness in different ways, as a result one may encounter the effect of “inconsistency” and “cacophony” in educational attitudes of students. We can also allow the possibility of situations in which a teacher, pursuing the goals of competence development of students that he may understand in a specific way, might not really develop and liberate the students’ thinking, but rather standardize and primitize its content, encouraging those forms of thinking and communication that *seem* optimal and progressive, not being such in reality. It is necessary to bear in mind the possibility of not quite qualified pedagogical practices, via which students can be harmed by introducing various cliches and stereotypical codes of thinking into their consciousness. In this context, “visible pedagogics” may turn out to be much less dangerous because of their “visibility” and transparency: since a teacher quite openly manifests his/her principles, rules and requirements, students always have the opportunity to identify, and then accept or reject them. It is much more difficult to determine how correct, humanistic and progressive the “invisible pedagogics” are in reality because of “their discursive rules are known only to the transmitter” [9]. As a result, it becomes much more difficult for students to protect themselves from unskilled intrusion into their private world and from arbitrary coding/programming of their consciousness, from attempts to construct their inner world according to inexplicable attitudes of external actors.

The deconstruction theory of education discusses the possibility of transforming the conceptual foundations of learning process, in which students can play an active role, showing agreement or disagreement with changing of their conceptual attitudes. In the concept of Allosteric Learning Model by A. Jordan, one can find an analysis of deconstructive educational practices carried out by a student himself. The process of assimilation of

knowledge is the result of the process of transforming existing concepts, where the main actor is only the student himself. The acquisition of knowledge involves an action of its elaboration through which a student... produces new values that are most suitable for solving the formulated problems [6]. In the context of deconstruction theory not so teaching methods (how teaching) as learning context (what learning) have great importance because they can stimulate intellectual creativity of students or, conversely, stay them indifferent due to its banality and superficiality.

According to A. Jordan, new knowledge resonates with the already existing information system of a student, as a result a variety of effects can occur, from distortion and mutation of information to its creative transformation. "To accept new knowledge means to include it in an already functioning conceptual structure. The new view replaces the old one, rebuilding the previous conceptual structures. What fundamentally changes in the student's thoughts is not information, but the conceptual "plexus" (lattice) that connects this information and produces new meanings for answering the question posed. Knowledge is not transmitted, it arises at the time of its elaboration, when the student's conceptual system, encountering new information and mobilizing existing ideas, produces a new system of meanings that are more suitable for solving problems formulated by the students themselves" [6, p. 309].

Similar conceptual attitudes can be found in the theory of D. Mezirov, who analyzed the basic principles of "transformative education" of adults, which results in a "paradigm shift" in their cognitive and normative-value orientations, generating radical transformations of their "personal paradigms". However, unlike A. Jordan, who believed that the resonant conjugation of new information and the already formed conceptual "lattice" became the basis for self-constitution of the students' worldview, D. Mezirov emphasizes the importance of radical discrepancies between the student's ideas and the knowledge that he/she perceives, the importance of occurrence of the so-called "disorienting dilemma", which "represents a mismatch between what a person already assumes as truth and what he/she just heard and read" [10]. The presence of such a discrepancy prompts a student to actively overestimate and rethink the existing worldview

experience, creatively reconfigure, transform it with the aim of reintegration into a new social and educational context.

In the future, it is necessary to consider the problem of the deconstruction of classical/innovative teaching practices, which implies the decentration of each of them from the “main” position and the recognition of the importance of each of them in a certain context. It is necessary to clarify the relationship between lecture and discussion interaction, monologue and dialogue, classical and innovative learning methods in the context of the postmodern theory of deconstruction.

References

1. Батаева, Е. (2019). Когнитивные и метакогнитивные способности обучающихся в контексте смарт-образования. *Образование и наука (=The Education and Science)*, 4(21), с. 36–59.
2. Батаева, Е. (2015). Условия коммуникативной солидарности в диверсифицированном обществе. *Гуманитарний часопис*, 2, с. 12–18.
3. Bataeva, K. (2016). Communicative and instrumental models of educational process in modern philosophy and sociology of education. *Гуманитарний часопис*, 3, p. 5–11.
4. Батаева, Е. (2015). Коммуникативные и инструментальные стратегии в системе высшего образования. *Вчені записки ХГУ «НУА»*, т. 21, с. 279–289.
5. Деррида, Ж. (2000). *О грамматологии*. М.: Ad Marginem, 521 с.
6. Жиордан, А. (2013). Аллостерическая модель и современные теории обучения. В: *Теоретические вопросы образования* [online]. Минск: БГУ. Available at: <http://elib.bsu.by/handle/123456789/104669>.
7. Батаева, Е.В. (ред.). (2017). *От коммуникативного действия к практикам деконструкции в современном образовании*. Харьков: Изд-во НУА, 204 с.
8. Bauman, Z. (1992). *Intimations of Postmodernity*. London, Routledge, 232 p.
9. Bernstein, B. (2009). Class, codes and control. In: *The Structuring of Pedagogic Discourse: IV*. London, Routledge, 246 p.
10. Mezirow, J. (1991). How Critical Reflection triggers Transformative Learning. In: *Fostering critical reflection in adulthood*. [online]. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers. URL: <http://www.ln.edu.hk/osl/conference2011/output/breakout/20Mezirow.pdf>.

References

1. Bataeva, E. (2019). Kognitivnye i metakognitivnye sposobnosti obuchajushhihsja v kontekste smart-obrazovanija [Cognitive and metacognitive abilities of students in the context of smart education]. *Obrazovanie i nauka*, 4(21), pp. 36–59.
2. Bataeva, E. (2015). Uslovija kommunikativnoj solidarnosti v diversificirovannom obshchestve [The conditions of communicative solidarity in a diversified society]. *Gumanitarnij chasopis*, 2, pp.12–18.
3. Bataeva, K. (2016). Communicative and instrumental models of educational process in modern philosophy and sociology of education. *Humanitarian Journal*, 3, pp. 5–11.
4. Bataeva, E. (2015). Kommunikativnye i instrumental'nye strategii v sisteme vysshego obrazovanija [Communicative and instrumental strategies in higher education]. *Vcheni zapiski HGU «NUA»*, vol.21, pp. 279–289.
5. Derrida, J. (2000). *Of Grammatology*. Moscow: Ad Marginem, pp.7-107. (in Russian).
6. Giordan, A. (2013). The allosteric learning model and current theories about learning. In: *Theoretical questions of education* [online]. Minsk: BSU. Available at: <http://elib.bsu.by/handle/123456789/104669> (in Russian).
7. Bataeva, E.V. (ed.). (2017). *Ot kommunikativnogo dejstvija k praktikam dekonstrukcii v sovremennom obrazovanii* [From communicative action to deconstruction practices in modern education]. Har'kov: Izd-vo NUA, 204 p.
8. Bauman, Z. (1992). *Intimations of Postmodernity*. London, Routledge, 232 p.
9. Bernstein, B. (2009). Class, codes and control. In: *The Structuring of Pedagogic Discourse: IV*. London, Routledge, 246 p.
10. Mezirow, J. (1991). How Critical Reflection triggers Transformative Learning. In: *Fostering critical reflection in adulthood*. [online]. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers. URL: <http://www.ln.edu.hk/osl/conference2011/output/breakout/20Mezirow.pdf>.